
Preparation and Properties of Supported Nano-MoS₂ Composite Electrode

Mande Qiu*, Xu Bian, Mengli Shang, Yanlong Cui

College of Chemistry and Environmental Science, Hebei University, Baoding 071002, People's Republic of China
*Email: hbuqmd@sina.cn

Abstract The nano-MoS₂ composite electrode was successfully prepared by one-step hydrothermal method using foamed nickel as the skeleton substrate. XRD and SEM were used to investigate the effects of different molybdenum to sulfur ratios on the morphology and phase of the electrode. On this basis, the electrochemical properties of the electrode and the performance of electrocatalytic degradation of methylene blue (MB) were investigated. The electrochemical and electrocatalytic degradation performance of the electrodes were investigated, and the electrocatalytic mechanism and electrocatalytic kinetics were discussed. Moreover, the effects of pH, voltage, and electrolyte on the catalytic performance were investigated, respectively. Especially, when used nano-MoS₂ as electrochemical electrode, it displayed excellent electrochemical performance with a decolorization rate of MB is 100% at pH=12.

Keywords MoS₂; foamed nickel; electrocatalytic; electrochemical performance

1. Introduction

The development of electrocatalytic oxidation technology began in the 1930s, and it can be applied to deal with various heavy metal ions in wastewater [1-3]. Electrocatalytic oxidation technology is an environmentally friendly and effective method, which has potential for removal of organic pollutants from wastewaters [4-6].

Molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) as a representative layered 2D with a large surface area, which can quickly adsorb organic pollutants on the surface of the electrode to achieve oxidative degradation [7-9]. As a semiconductor material, MoS₂ has a special band structure. Under the applied voltage, the electrons in the valence band of MoS₂ can enter the conduction band region across the forbidden band. In the valence band region, a special electro-excitation hole with strong electron-trapping ability is formed, and the hole can realize strong capture of the surface electron of the organic pollutant, and the redox reaction degrades it. Nevertheless, the poor conductivity of MoS₂ and the low electron transport rate limit its development in the electrode. Therefore, the conductive transmission efficiency can be improved by means of load, modification and modification [10-12].

Therefore, the experiment put foam nickel into the PPL lining with foamed nickel as the substrate [13-15]. First, nanorod nickel sulfide is formed on the surface of nickel, and clustered MoS₂ is grown on the surface of rod-shaped nickel sulfide to form a supported nano-MoS₂ composite electrode. Studies have shown that NiS has a strong electrical conductivity. Moreover, the synergistic effect of the excellent electron transport capacity of NiS and the special band structure of MoS₂ can improve the dye degradation rate.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials synthesis

$(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{NH}_2)_2\text{CS}$ were dissolved in 8 mL water according to a certain ratio of sulfur to molybdenum. The pH value was adjusted to 2 with HCl. Afterwards, the mixed solution and pretreated foamed Ni were transferred into a stainless Teflon-lined autoclave. The stainless Teflon lined autoclave was placed in an electric drying oven, heated at 220°C for 24h, and then naturally cooled to room temperature. After repeatedly washing the as-prepared products with distilled water and ethanol, and dried at 60 °C for 12 h.

2.2. Characterization

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were gained from a D8 ADVANCE (Bruker, Switzerland) with Cu α radiation at a scan rate of 8°/min. The microscopic morphology of MoS_2 was examined by a JSM-7500F field emission scanning electron microscope (Jeol Ltd, Japan). The CHI660E electrochemical workstation was used to test the electrochemical performance. Other test instruments also include TU-1900 dual beam UV-visible spectrophotometer, LD4-2A high speed centrifuge and Type 79-1 magnetic heating stirrer.

2.3. Electrochemical measurements

The CHI660E electrochemical workstation was used to test the electrochemical performance. We used a 2M solution of KOH dissolved in water as the electrolyte and composite electrode as a working electrode. The foil was used as the counter electrode, and Ag/AgCl is used as reference electrode.

The MB solution was placed in a 50 mL beaker at a concentration of 20 mg/L, and the pH of the solution was adjusted with HCl and NaOH. The composite electrode is used as the anode, and the platinum plate electrode is used as the cathode for electrocatalytic degradation of MB. The absorbance value A was measured every 10 min with stirring at a fixed speed, and the decolorization rate of electrocatalysis was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Decolorization rate} = (A_0 - A_t) / A_0 \times 100\%$$

Where A_0 is the initial concentrations of MB; A_t is the concentrations of MB in the solution.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 1: SEM images of electrodes under different Mo:S ratio conditions(a, d) 1:2(b, e) 1:3(c, f) 1:4(g, h) section(i)amplification

Figure 1 shows some SEM images of the MoS₂ composite electrode under different molybdenum-sulfur ratio. As shown in Figure 1a and 1d, when the molybdenum to sulfur ratio is 1:2, NiS nanorods are formed on the surface of the foamed nickel, and no obvious clustered MoS₂ appeared. When the molybdenum-sulfur ratio was 1:3, MoS₂ nanosheets were observed on the SEM photograph. Moreover, when the ratio continues to increase to 1:4, epitaxially grown MoS₂ nanosheets evenly distributed on the CNFs. The skeleton structure of the foamed nickel is not destroyed, indicating that the optimum ratio of molybdenum to sulfur is 1:4. It can be seen from the cross-section that foamed nickel provides a substrate environment for the growth of nanorods [15]. When the proportion of thiourea continues to increase, part of the sulfur in the thiourea is used to produce NiS, and the other part is used to reduce the ammonium paramolybdate. The generated nanorod NiS provides a substrate for MoS₂. It can be seen that the clustered MoS₂ is tightly surrounded by the nanorod NiS to form a composite electrode with special morphology.

Figure 2: XRD patterns of the composite electrode (a) 1:2(b) 1:3 (c) 1:4

As shown in Fig. 2, the X-ray diffraction patterns of composite electrode under different molybdenum-sulfur ratio. The XRD diffraction peaks at 18.353°, 30.194°, 32.128°, 35.595°, 37.321°, 40.396°, 48.802°, 50.094°, 52.596°, 56.169°, 57.355°, 59.645° and 67.284° coincide with the NiS. The diffraction peaks at 14.636°, 34.113°, 39.758° and 58.664° correspond to the MoS₂. As the molybdenum-sulfur ratio increases, the characteristic diffraction peak of MoS₂ becomes sharper and the diffraction intensity increases.

Figure 3: Cyclic voltammetry curves of electrodes under different Mo:S (a) 1:2(b) 1:3(c) 1:4

Figure 4: AC impedance spectrum of the electrode under different Mo: S(a)1:4(b) 1:3 (c) 1:2

The CV curves of composite electrode under different molybdenum-sulfur ratio are shown in Fig. 3. When the molybdenum-sulfur ratio is 1:2, there are no obvious oxidation and reduction peaks during the scans. When the ratio is 1:4, the reduction peak appears at 0.81 V and reduction peak at 1.6 V. The oxidation and reduction peaks keep highly overlapped from the second cycle. It indicates good electrochemical reversibility and electrocatalytic effect of the composite electrode [16,17]. The Nyquist plots of composite electrode are shown in Fig. 4. The molybdenum-sulfur ratio is 1:4 exhibits larger charge transfer resistance. As the molybdenum-sulfur ratio increases, the surface of the NiS nanorods grows more clusters of MoS₂, which enhances the electron transport rate of the electrode and accelerates the progress of the redox reaction, resulting in a decrease in polarization resistance.

Figure 5: UV-Vis absorption spectra of electrode electrocatalyzed degradation of MB solution at different pH

Figure 6: The effect of MB pH on the efficiency of NiS/MoS₂ electrode

Figure 7: UV-Vis absorption spectra of electrode electrocatalyzed degradation of MB solution at different cell voltages

Figure 8: The effect of cell voltage on the efficiency of NiS/MoS₂ electrode

Fig.7 shows the UV-Vis absorption spectra of electrode electrocatalyzed degradation of MB solution at different cell voltages. When the catalytic voltage is 3 V, the maximum absorption peak position is still high after 70 minutes, and the attenuation is small. In contrast, the maximum absorption peak of MB cannot be observed when the catalytic voltage is 10 V. As show in Fig. 8, as the applied voltage is gradually increased, the decolorization effect is significantly increased. When the applied voltage reaches 10 V, the presence of MB cannot be detected in the aqueous solution after 70 minutes.

Figure 9: The effect of different dyes on the efficiency of NiS/MoS₂ electrode

As shown in Fig.9, The decolorization effect of the methyl orange solution is not very significantly about 20%. However, the decolorization effect of rhodamine and methylene blue solution is better, and the decolorization rate can reach 80% at 70 min. The main reason is that there is a relatively stable structure in the molecule of methyl orange, which requires more energy to catalyze degradation in the electrocatalytic process. Molecular structures of methylene blue and rhodamine B are easily destroyed, and the energy required for electrocatalysis is small, showing a high electrocatalytic effect.

Figure 10: The effect of electrolyte species on the efficiency of NiS/MoS₂ electrode

As can be seen from the results shown in Fig. 10, the species of electrolyte has a significant effect on the electrocatalytic effect. When the electrolyte is sodium sulfate, the catalytic efficiency is as high as 80%. When the electrolyte is sodium sulfate, the sulfate ion is oxidized at the anode portion of the electrode to form persulfate. The persulfate can directly participate in the oxidation of methylene blue to increase the electrocatalytic efficiency.

Figure 11: Kinetics of electrocatalytic degradation under different catalytic voltage conditions

Table 1: Kinetic parameters of electrocatalytic degradation under different catalytic voltage conditions

(V)	equation	R ²	Kapp (min ⁻¹)	Total reaction rate (mg/(L·min))
3	y=0.0072x+0.2074	0.95573	0.0072	0.144
5	y=0.0126x+0.2997	0.94884	0.0126	0.252
7	y=0.0169x+0.4319	0.97927	0.0169	0.338
10	y=0.0407x+0.6742	0.95938	0.0407	0.814

In order to investigate the kinetic mechanism of the electrocatalytic process in depth, we used Langmuir-Hinshelwood pseudo-first-order kinetic model to fit the catalytic data at different catalytic voltages [20,21]. The equation is as follows:

$$\ln \left(\frac{C_0}{C_t} \right) = k_{app} \cdot t$$

(Kapp-the absorption rate constant, C₀-the initial concentration of MB, C_t-the concentrations of MB in the solution after adsorption). It can be seen from the equation that the fitting slope corresponds to the pseudo-first-order kinetic constant of the reaction, and then the total reaction rate under different conditions can be calculated by the kinetic constant. At room temperature, methylene blue was placed in a beaker for electrocatalytic experiments. The catalytic voltages were adjusted to 3, 5, 7, and 10 V, respectively, and the absorbance was measured every 10 min. As shown in Fig. 11, the fitted graphs under different catalytic voltage conditions all show a great linear relationship, and the slope increases with the increase of the catalytic voltage. The total reaction rates under different catalytic voltage conditions were 0.144 mg/(L·min), 0.252 mg/(L·min), 0.338 mg/(L·min), and 0.814 mg/(L·min), respectively. The total reaction rate gradually increased with the gradual increase of the catalytic voltage. The fitting results under different catalytic voltage conditions are in good agreement with the pseudo-first-order kinetic equation. Therefore, the process of electrocatalytic degradation of methylene blue may be that the electrode adsorbs methylene blue dye molecules on the surface of the electrode and then degrades it by electrocatalytic oxidation.

4. Conclusion

In summary, the nano-MoS₂ composite electrode was successfully prepared by one-step hydrothermal method using foamed nickel as the skeleton substrate. Moreover, our work highlights atomic understanding of the reaction kinetics of the NiS/MoS₂ electrocatalytic. The results as follow:

- (1) The nano-MoS₂ composite electrode was successfully prepared. When the molybdenum-sulfur ratio was 1:4, the product showed a regular nanorod structure and flower cluster structure MoS₂ grew around the NiS.
- (2) Electrochemical performance test results show that nanorod array electrodes have good conductivity and reusability. The CV cycles are well-overlapped and illustrates the good stability of the NiS/MoS₂ electrode.
- (3) The prepared optimal electrode exhibits excellent electrocatalytic performance. Research has shown that the electrocatalytic degradation rate under alkaline conditions is higher than that under acidic conditions. When the pH is 12, the decolorization rate of MB is as high as 100%. The degradation rate of MB is up to 99%, when the catalytic voltage is 10 V. Moreover, the process of electrocatalytic degradation of methylene blue may be that the electrode adsorbs methylene blue dye molecules on the surface of the electrode and then degrades it by electrocatalytic oxidation.

References

- [1]. Huang T, Liu L, Tao J, et al. Microbial fuel cells coupling with the three-dimensional electro-Fenton technique enhances the degradation of methyl orange in the wastewater [J]. Environmental Science and Pollution Research, 2018, 25(18):17989-18000.
- [2]. Hai G, Jia X, Zhang K, et al. High-performance oxygen evolution catalyst using two-dimensional ultrathin metal-organic frameworks nanosheets [J]. Nano Energy, 2018, 44:345-352.
- [3]. Li XH, Jin XD, Zhao NN, Angelidaki I, Zhang YF (2017) Novel bioelectro-Fenton technology for azo dye wastewater treatment using microbial reverse-electrodialysis electrolysis cell [J]. Bioresour Technol, 2017, 228:322–329.
- [4]. Yun Z, Lifei S, Na S, et al. Bifunctional and Efficient CoS₂-C@MoS₂ Core-Shell Nanofiber Electrocatalyst for Water Splitting [J]. ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng. 2019, 7:2899-2905.
- [5]. Zahra Mohammadpour, Seyyed Hossein Abdollahi, and Afsaneh Safavi Sugar-Based Natural Deep Eutectic Mixtures as Green Intercalating Solvents for High-Yield Preparation of Stable MoS₂ Nanosheets: Application to Electrocatalysis of Hydrogen Evolution Reaction [J]. ACS Appl. Energy Mater, 2018, 1: 5896-5906.
- [6]. Jing dong L, Yang J, Ming C, et al. A novel green and safe dearsenization of white phosphorus by selective electrocatalytic oxidation [J]. Separation and Purification Technology, 2019, 213: 314–321.
- [7]. Chun yong Z, Jiayue D, Min L, et al. The role of nitrite in electrocatalytic oxidation of phenol: An unexpected nitration process relevant to groundwater remediation with boron-doped diamond electrode [J]. Journal of Hazardous Materials, 2019, 373: 547-557.
- [8]. Dawei C, Yuqin Z, Shuang yin W. Surface chemical-functionalization of ultrathin two-dimensional nanomaterials for electrocatalysis [J]. Materials Today Energy, 2019, 12: 250-268.
- [9]. Yuan X F, Li X M, Zhang X, et al. MoS₂ vertically grown on graphene with efficient electrocatalytic activity in Pt-free dye-sensitized solar cells [J]. Journal of Alloys and Compounds, 2018, 731: 685-692.
- [10]. Lei Y, Jijia Z, Chao F, et al. MoS₂ nanosheet/MoS₂ flake homostructures for efficient electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution [J]. Mater. Res. Express, 2019, 6: 085005.
- [11]. Daniel Escalera-López, Ross Griffin, Mark Isaacs et al. MoS₂ and WS₂ nanocone arrays: Impact of surface topography on the hydrogen evolution electrocatalytic activity and mass transport [J]. 2018.
- [12]. Wei L, Ran B, Guoxue L, et al. 3D Interconnected MoS₂ with Enlarged Interlayer Spacing Grown on Carbon Nanofibers as a Flexible Anode toward Superior Sodium-ion Batteries [J]. ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces, 2018, 10: 26982-26989.

- [13]. Zhao C J, Zhang Y X, and Qian X Z. MoS₂/RGO/Ni₃S₂ nanocomposite in-situ grown on Ni Foam substrate and its high electrochemical performance [J]. *Electrochimica Acta*, 2016, 198: 135-143.
- [14]. Xiong F, Cai Z, Qu L, et al. Three-Dimensional Crumpled Reduced Graphene Oxide/MoS₂Nanoflowers: A Stable Anode for Lithium-Ion Batteries [J]. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 2015, 7(23):12625-12630.
- [15]. Xue D, Zhao-Peng D, Li-Hua H, Large-scale synthesis of NiS@N and S co-doped carbon mesoporous tubule as high performance anode for lithium-ion battery [J]. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 2019, 788: 984-992.
- [16]. Ya qiong Z, Hua chao T, Tao L, et al. Vertically Oxygen-Incorporated MoS₂ Nanosheets Coated on Carbon Fibers for Sodium-Ion Batteries [J]. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2018, 10: 35206-35215.
- [17]. Hang Z, Jinhua W, Jian long L, et al. A flexible three-dimensional MoS₂/carbon architecture derived from melamine foam as free-standing anode for high performance lithium-ion batteries [J]. *Applied Surface Science*, 2018, 462:337-343.
- [18]. Hu W H, Han G Q, Dai F N, et al. Effect of pH on the growth of MoS₂ (002) plane and electrocatalytic activity for HER [J]. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 2016: 294-299.
- [19]. Palmer R. MoS₂ and WS₂ nanocone arrays: Impact of surface topography on the hydrogen evolution electrocatalytic activity and mass transport [J]. *Applied Materials Today*, 2018, 11: 70–81.
- [20]. Eseoghene H. Umukoro, Neeraj Kumar, Jane C. Ngila, et al. Expanded graphite supported p-n MoS₂-SnO₂ heterojunction nanocomposite electrode for enhanced photo-electrocatalytic degradation of a pharmaceutical pollutant [J]. *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry*, 2018, 827: 193–203.
- [21]. Dan W, Ya Xiu Zh, Qiang L, et al. Electrosorption of Methylene Blue from Aqueous Solution on Graphene-Titanium Electrode: Adsorption Kinetics Studies [J]. *International Journal of Chemical Reactor Engineering*, 2018.